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Patricia Ruiz, Lucía Celada, Susana Seseña, María Llanos Palop

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1 ***Leuconostoc mesenteroides* in the brewing process: a controversial role**

2

3 **Patricia Ruiz, Lucía Celada, Susana Seseña*, María Llanos Palop**

4 *Department of Analytical Chemistry and Food Technology, Environmental Sciences and*

5 *Biochemistry Faculty, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Carlos III, s/n, 45071 Toledo,*

6 *Spain.*

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22 * Corresponding author. Tel.: +34-925-268-800.

23 *E-mail address:* susana.sprieto@uclm.es (S. Seseña)

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25

26 **Abstract**

27 The aim of this study was to characterize 29 *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates isolated during
28 a brewing process in order to determine their potential contributions to the process and the product.
29 In order to achieve this aim different enzymatic activities, the exopolysaccharide (EPS) production,
30 the antagonistic activity, the beer spoilage ability and the production of lactic acid and diacetyl in
31 beer, were assessed. *Ln. mesenteroides* isolates showed weak acidifying activity, and only 28% of
32 them produced decreases in pH higher than 0.5 units after a 24 hours period of incubation. The
33 isolates were also scarcely proteolytic and did not produce EPS. Results from enzymatic activity
34 assay showed that some of the isolates produced β -galactosidase and α - and β -glucosidases while
35 none produced β -glucuronidase.

36 All the isolates inhibited the growth of both *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*,
37 although none of them inhibited *Pediococcus acidilactici*. When *Lactobacillus brevis* was used as
38 an indicator, 44.8% of the isolates showed antagonistic activity. The beer-spoilage ability assay
39 showed that only 5 of the 29 isolates were able to grow in beer but none of them harboured *horA* or
40 *horC* genes. However, the growth of these isolates in beer did not produce an excess of D-lactic
41 acid or diacetyl.

42 These findings show that the presence of any of the characterized isolates during the brewing
43 process or in the bottled beer would not have a negative impact. On the contrary, the findings reveal
44 interesting and potentially beneficial effects.

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47 **Keywords:** *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*; Beer; Antagonistic activity; Beer spoilage; Enzymatic
48 activity; Exopolysaccharide.

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51 1. Introduction

52 Beer has been recognized for centuries as a safe beverage. However, the presence of
53 microorganisms, both bacteria and yeasts, different from those used to carry out the fermentation,
54 has been displayed at various stages of the production process. Among the bacteria, both Gram (+)
55 and Gram (-) are present, with lactic acid bacteria (LAB) being isolated at almost every stage of the
56 malting and brewing process (Bokulich & Barmforth, 2013). The role of LAB in this process is
57 controversial and they are recognized as the most hazardous bacteria in breweries, responsible for
58 approximately 70% of the microbial beer-spoilage incidents. During growth, they produce an
59 excess of turbidity and acidity as well as off-odours, due to the production of diacetyl and hydrogen
60 sulfide (Fernandez & Simpson, 1995; Hartnett, Vaughan, & van Sinderen, 2002; Sakamoto &
61 Konings, 2003), which negatively affect the quality of beer, producing important economic losses
62 for the brewing industry (Back, 1994; March, Manclús, Abad, Navarro, & Montoya, 2005;
63 Sakamoto & Konings, 2003; Vaughan, Eijsink, O'Sullivan, O'Hanlon, & van Sinderen, 2001).

64 However, some authors affirm that it is not categorically possible to define LAB as having a
65 negative impact as they may perform some necessary and beneficial functions (Bokulich &
66 Barmforth, 2013; Haikara, Uljas, & Suurnäkki, 1993). Through their ability to produce
67 antimicrobial substances, these bacteria may prevent the growth of harmful organisms improving
68 safety of beer (Boivin & Malanda, 1997; Haikara & Laitila, 1995). Positive effects of LAB in food,
69 including some beverages, are well known (Okada, 2002), but these bacteria have rarely been
70 explored in the brewing process.

71 LAB in beer belong mainly to the *Lactobacillus* and *Pediococcus* genera (Bokulich & Bamford,
72 2013; March, Manclús, Abad, Navarro, & Montoya, 2005; Sakamoto & Konings, 2003), but the
73 presence of isolates belonging to *Lactococcus* and *Leuconostoc*, albeit in lower frequency, has also
74 been shown (Garofalo et al., 2015; Justé et al., 2014; Suzuki, Asano, Iijima, & Kitamoto, 2008).

75 *Leuconostoc* is a genus whose presence in some fermented foods contributes to the organoleptic
76 properties since it produces acetaldehyde, diacetyl and acetoin from lactate and citrate (McSweeney
77 & Sousa, 2000). In addition, it possesses other capabilities, which enable it to produce dextrans
78 from sucrose (Vedamuthu, 1994) and different enzymes, such as proteinase, lipases and
79 aminopeptidases (Macedo & Malcata, 1997). In the brewing process, *Leuconostoc* species have
80 been described to be present in both malt (Kaur, 2009; Vaughan, Eijsink, O'Sullivan, O'Hanlon, &
81 van Sinderen, 2001) and during the malting process (Bokulich & Mills, 2012; Justé et al., 2014)
82 yielding an improvement in malt quality, which may shorten lautering and wort filtration time
83 (Haikara, Uljas, & Suurnäkki, 1993). On the other hand, Giles-Gómez et al. (2016), in a study
84 carried out on a Mexican alcoholic beverage different from beer, reported that the presence of
85 *Leuconostoc* species can be beneficial due to their probiotic properties. However, Suzuki, Asano,
86 Iijima, & Kitamoto (2008) reported their potential spoilage ability, as ropy slime producers; though
87 it should be noted that the frequency of spoilage incidents by isolates of *Leuconostoc* in beer is
88 lower than 1%.

89 A recent study by Poveda, Ruiz, Seseña, & Palop (2017) showed the presence of *Leuconostoc*
90 *mesenteroides* strains in samples taken at different stages during a craft brewing process and the
91 objective of this study was to assess these strains in order to understand their potential positive and
92 negative impact on the process or on the product.

93

94 **2. Material and methods**

95 **2.1. Bacterial isolates and growth conditions**

96 Twenty-nine *Leuconostoc (Ln.) mesenteroides* isolates were assessed. They had been previously
97 isolated from samples taken at different stages during a craft brewing process (Poveda, Ruiz,
98 Seseña, & Palop, 2017) and were maintained frozen (-80°C) in MRS (de Man, Rogosa, & Sharpe,

99 1960) broth (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) containing 20% (v/v) glycerol. Isolates were revitalized
100 by cultivation in the same broth and incubated at 30°C for 48 h in aerobic conditions.

101 **2.2. Characterization of isolates**

102 *2.2.1. Enzymatic activities*

103 The acidifying and proteolytic activities were tested as described by Nieto-Arribas, Seseña,
104 Poveda, Palop, & Cabezas (2010). For the acidifying activity, pH was measured using a Crison pH-
105 meter (Crison, Barcelona, Spain) after 4 h and 24 h of incubation at 30°C, and the values were
106 expressed as Δ pH. For the proteolytic activity, the o-phthaldehyde (oPA) method as described in
107 Church, Swaisgood, Porter, & Catignani (1983) was used and the results were expressed as mM
108 glycine/L.

109 For the autolytic activity, cells from exponentially growing cultures (Optical Density (OD) at
110 650 nm = 0.7–0.8) in MRS broth were harvested by centrifugation at 10,000 x g for 10 min at 4°C
111 and the pellet washed and resuspended in 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). The cell
112 suspension was incubated at 30°C and the lysis was monitored after 30 min, 4 h and 24 h of
113 incubation by recording the decrease in OD₆₅₀ using a Beckman DU-530 spectrophotometer. The
114 percentage of lysis was determined as $100 - (A1/A2 \times 100)$, where A1 and A2 were the lowest and
115 the highest value of the OD₆₅₀ measured during incubation, respectively.

116 For all tests, three cultures of each isolate were analysed and the measurements were performed
117 in duplicate.

118 The presence of another 19 enzymatic activities was assessed using the API-ZYM galleries
119 (BioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France) in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. After
120 incubation, ZYM A and ZYM B reagents were added and a positive reaction was recorded when
121 there was a change of colour. The intensity of the colour was rated as light (+), medium (++) or
122 dark (+++).

123 *2.2.2. Exopolysaccharides (EPS) production*

124 Exopolysaccharide (EPS) production was tested as described by Ribeiro et al. (2013) using
125 both, MRS agar medium containing 2% (w/v) of one of the following carbon sources: sucrose,
126 glucose, lactose or fructose (all purchased from Oxoid) and Mayeux agar (BIOKAR-Diagnostics,
127 Solabia Group, Francia).

128 Five microlitres of the revitalized isolate in MRS broth were inoculated in each of the plates as
129 a drop and plates were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours, both in aerobic and anaerobic conditions
130 (GenBox/GenBag BioMérieux). Mucoidity of colonies was determined by visual appearance and
131 isolates producing slimy colonies were regarded as positive (Smitinont et al., 1999).

132 2.2.3. Antagonistic activity against potential spoilage bacteria

133 The spot test, as set forth in Garcia et al. (2016) with slight modifications, was used. Five
134 microliters of an overnight culture in MRS broth of the analysed isolate were spotted on the surface
135 of MRS agar plates and incubated at 30°C for 24 h in aerobic conditions.

136 Simultaneously, cultures of the bacteria used as indicators in an appropriate media were
137 prepared and incubated in optimal conditions until reaching absorbance values at 600 nm
138 (BECKMAN DU 530 spectrophotometer) between 0.8 and 1 (approximately 8 log cfu/mL). The
139 strains used as indicators and the conditions used for their growth were as follow: *Lactobacillus*
140 (*Lb.*) *brevis* CECT 4121^T and *Pediococcus (P.) acidilactici* CECT 5765^T, both cultivated in MRS
141 broth at 30°C, *Escherichia (E.) coli* CECT 45 and *Staphylococcus (St.) aureus* CECT 86^T, both
142 cultivated in Tryptone Soy Broth (TSB) at 37°C. All were purchased from the Spanish Type
143 Culture Collection (CECT).

144 An adequate volume of the indicator bacteria culture was mixed with 7 mL of soft (0.7% w/v
145 agar) MRS or Trypticase Soy Agar (Pronadisa), depending on the species, to reach a final viable
146 count of 10⁶ CFU/mL and the mixture was poured over the spot-inoculated MRS agar plates. The
147 plates were again incubated in optimal conditions for each indicator, and the antagonistic activity

148 was recorded as the diameter (mm) of growth inhibition zones around each spot. As reported by
149 Rouse, Sun, Vaughan, & Sinderen (2007) five possible results were recorded: (-) no inhibition halo
150 was observed; (+) diameter of halo ≤ 1 cm; (++) diameter of halo between 1.1 and 1.9 cm; (+++)
151 diameter of the inhibition halo between 2 and 2.9 cm and (++++) diameter of inhibition halo ≥ 3
152 cm.

153 2.2.4. Beer spoilage ability

154 The beer spoilage potential was tested as described by Suzuki (2002). Degassed Ale beer (pH
155 4.4; 4.8% (v/v) alcohol content; 25 IBU) was adjusted to pH 4.2 with 1 M NaOH and sterilized by
156 filtration (0.45 μm pore size filters; Sartorius Stedim Biotech, Goettingen, Germany). Fifteen
157 millilitres of the beer were dispensed in sterile polypropylene tubes and inoculated with a culture of
158 the isolate analysed to reach approximately 10^5 cells/mL. The inoculated beers were incubated
159 anaerobically at 30°C for up to 60 days. Non-inoculated beer was used as a control.

160 A sample of beer was taken weekly and serially diluted in sterile saline solution, in order to be
161 plated in duplicate on MRS agar. Plates were incubated aerobically at 30°C for 48 h and the counts
162 expressed as colony forming units (cfu) per mL of beer.

163 In order to confirm that colonies grown on plates corresponded to the inoculated isolates, 10%
164 of the total number of colonies from countable MRS agar plates were picked at random and
165 together with a colony of the inoculated isolates grown on the same medium typed by RAPD-PCR
166 (Randomly Amplified Polymorphic DNA analysis) as described by Ruiz, Izquierdo, Seseña, &
167 Palop (2008). Subsequently, a comparison of the genetic profiles obtained was performed by using
168 the GelCompar version 4.0 analysis software (Applied Maths, Kortrijk, Belgium).

169 2.2.5. Determination for presence of *horA* and *horC* genes

170 Genomic DNA was obtained from well-developed single colonies on MRS agar following the
171 procedure described by Pérez-Martín, Seseña, Izquierdo, & Palop (2014). Isolates were tested for

172 the presence of *horA* and *horC* genes using the conditions outlined in Deng et al. (2014) and the
173 primers listed in Table 1. A PCR internal control, corresponding to the 16S rRNA coding gene was
174 included. *Lactobacillus paracollinoides* CECT 8644 was used as a positive control for both genes
175 in the reactions.

176 2.2.6. Lactic acid and diacetyl production in beer

177 The production of lactic acid and diacetyl was determined in the beers from the spoilage ability
178 assay in which counts had been obtained. At the end of the 60 day incubation period, the beer was
179 centrifuged (10,000 x g, 10 min, 4°C) and the cell-free supernatant was used for lactic acid and
180 diacetyl determinations.

181 The total diacetyl plus acetoin content was determined by a colorimetric test as described by
182 IDF Standard 149A (1997). The absorbance was measured at 525 nm using a Beckman DU-530
183 spectrophotometer. A calibration curve with diacetyl concentrations between 0 and 450 mg/L was
184 used.

185 D-lactic acid was determined using an enzymatic colorimetric method (Chemelex, S.A.
186 Barcelona, Spain) following the manufacturer's recommendations.

187 2.3. Statistical analysis

188 A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to the results of the acidifying,
189 proteolytic and autolytic activities, using the Student-Newman-Keuls (S-N-K) test for comparison
190 of the means. A probability value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. For this
191 purpose, the SPSS software package version 22.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used.

192

193 3. Results and discussion

194 Table 2 shows the results for the acidifying activity. Slight decreases in pH were observed for
195 all the isolates after 4 h and 24 h of incubation with only 28% of the isolates showing a decrease in

196 pH higher than 0.5 units after 24 h incubation. Isolate F6-12 showed the highest acidifying activity
197 ($p < 0.05$) followed by isolates F7-14, F10-11, F2-5 and F7-18. Other authors (Ayad, Nashat, El-
198 Sadek, Metwaly, & El-Soda, 2004; Garabal, Rodriguez-Alonso, & Centeno, 2008; Nieto-Arribas,
199 Seseña, Poveda, Palop, & Cabezas, 2010) have reported low acidifying activity for *Leuconostoc*
200 isolates from different origins, in accordance with their heterofermentative metabolism.

201 Values for proteolytic activity ranged between 0.21 and 0.69 mmol glycine/L (Table 2) and
202 significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in values for this activity were found between isolates. The
203 *Leuconostoc* genus has been reported to be scarcely proteolytic (Ballesteros, Poveda, González-
204 Viñas, & Cabezas, 2006) but it is important to highlight that the values obtained in this study for
205 *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates from beer were twice or three times higher than those reported
206 by Garabal, Rodriguez-Alonso, & Centeno (2008) and Nieto-Arribas, Seseña, Poveda, Palop, &
207 Cabezas (2010) for isolates from cheeses.

208 With regard to autolytic activity, different behaviours were observed. For 66% of the isolates, a
209 rapid decrease in the optical density was observed during the first 4 h of incubation, while in the
210 remaining isolates the optical density was maintained throughout this time, and the decrease in the
211 optical density was observed after 24 h of incubation. Isolates F3-15 and F3-9 showed the highest
212 ($p < 0.05$) autolytic capacity after 24 h of incubation, with values significantly higher than those for
213 the remaining isolates. It is of note that some of the isolates showing high autolytic activity (i.e. F3-
214 9; F12-12; F4-15) were also between the most proteolytic (Table 2).

215 *Leuconostoc* isolates in this study showed a high autolysis rate, concurring with the results from
216 Aquilanti, Zannini, Zocchetti, Osimani, & Clementi (2007) and Nieto-Arribas, Seseña, Poveda,
217 Palop, & Cabezas (2010). The ability of strains to lyse and subsequently release intracellular
218 enzymes is a desirable trait when they are used as a starter in industrial processes because it
219 increases the rate for enzymatic reactions, which in turn can affect the organoleptic properties of the

220 products (Crow et al., 1995; Lepeuple et al., 1998). Therefore, it is possible to think that the high
221 autolytic activity of the isolates analyzed could have a positive effect on the brewing process.

222 None of the isolates produced esterases, lipases, β -glucuronidase, trypsin or α -fucosidase
223 (Table 3 and Supplementary Table S1). Results for esterases and lipases were in concordance with
224 Morandi, Cremonesi, Silvetti, & Brasca (2013) and Nieto-Arribas, Seseña, Poveda, Palop, &
225 Cabezas (2010), while Macedo & Malcata (1997) reported lipase activity in *Ln. mesenteroides* ssp.
226 *mesenteroides/dextranicum*, though after a long incubation period.

227 The inability to produce β -glucuronidase, which is associated with the induction of toxins,
228 mutagens, and carcinogenesis (Dabek, McCrae, Stevens, Ducan, & Louis, 2008), and trypsin is
229 considered a desirable property for strains to be used as probiotics (Tanner, Strzempko, Belsky, &
230 McKinley, 1985) although the absence of α -fucosidase activity would not be desirable, as this
231 enzyme has a relevant role in the intestinal colonization of bacteria (Salyers, West, Vercellotti, &
232 Wilkins, 1977).

233 Only eight enzymatic activities were detected in some of the isolates (Table 3). Among these
234 include the enzymes β -galactosidase which hydrolyzes lactose (De Verse et al., 2003); α -
235 glucosidase which breaks down starches and disaccharides into glucose and other products (Lee et
236 al., 2014) and β -glucosidase which converts glycosides into aglycones (Chun et al., 2007).

237 Consistent with the findings for other LAB (Papamanoli, Tzanetakis, Litopoulou-Tzanetaki, &
238 Kotzekidou, 2003; Lee et al., 2015), all *Ln. mesenteroides* isolates produced acid phosphatase and
239 naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase although the intensity of the colour produced during the
240 reactions for both enzymes differed with the isolates, and for some of them the results were
241 considered weak or inconclusive, especially for the naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase
242 (Supplementary Table S1).

243 The isolate B1-18, isolated from the filling tap, exhibited the highest number of activities (8)
244 and, in addition, for five of them (leucine and valine arylamidase, β -galactosidase, α - and β -

245 glucosidase) the intensity of the colour produced during the reaction was considered (++) or (+++)
246 (Table 3). The presence of β -galactosidase and α - and β -glucosidases make this isolate potentially
247 interesting from a technological point of view. β -galactosidase is an enzyme widely used in the
248 dairy industry to improve lactose digestion and convert it into short-chain fatty acids that are
249 beneficial materials for the host (Naidu, Bidlack, & Clemens, 1999). The presence of β -
250 glucosidases is related to the appearance of desirable aromas and tastes in cheese (Monteagudo-
251 Mera et al., 2011) and wine (Pérez-Martín, Seseña, Izquierdo, Martín, & Palop, 2012) because the
252 free aglycones released from glycosides are more reactive and volatile. In addition, it has been
253 reported that β -glucosidase produces galacto-oligosaccharides which stimulate growth and
254 colonization of bifidobacteria in the intestine (Sako, Matsumoto, & Tanaka, 1999), and therefore
255 microorganisms producing this enzyme would be acting as a probiotic. It would be advisable to
256 carry out complementary analysis in order to determine the probiotic potential of B1-18 isolate.

257 Results from tests for EPS production using MRS agar medium containing 2% (w/v) of sucrose,
258 glucose, lactose or fructose and Mayeux agar were negative for all the isolates, both in aerobic and
259 anaerobic incubation, contrary to the findings in Torres-Rodríguez et al. (2014) for *Leuconostoc*
260 species isolated from pulque, a Mexican alcoholic beverage. EPS production can cause turbidity
261 and viscosity in the beer, consequently being an undesirable trait.

262 Of all the properties considered desirable in microorganisms used for food fermentations, the
263 antimicrobial activity is perhaps one of the most important in order to prevent the potential risk to
264 consumers of contracting foodborne diseases. The 29 *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates were
265 assayed against *Lactobacillus (Lb.) brevis* CECT 4121^T and *Pediococcus (P.) acidilactici* CECT
266 5765^T, two spoilage bacteria in beer (Rouse, Sun, Vaughan, & Sinderen, 2007), and *Escherichia*
267 (*E. coli* CECT 45 and *Staphylococcus (St.) aureus* CECT 86^T), both considered potential pathogens
268 (Macaluso, Fiorenza, Gaglio, Mancuso, & Scatassa, 2016).

269 It is worth noting that all the isolates were able to inhibit the growth of both *E. coli* and *St.*
270 *aureus*, although differences in the antagonistic activity for both bacteria were observed between
271 the isolates. Isolate B1-18 was found to be one of the most active in inhibiting the growth of both
272 bacteria. Contrarily, none of the isolates inhibited the growth of *P. acidilactici*.

273 Differences between isolates were also observed when *Lb. brevis* was used as an indicator and
274 while 37.9% of the isolates did not inhibit the growth of this species, 44.8% showed antagonistic
275 activity. For the remaining isolates, results were not definitive because inhibition halos for
276 replicates gave different results.

277 A comparison of these results to those of other authors has shown important differences. So
278 while *Leuconostoc* isolates from Morandi, Cremonesi, Silveti, & Brasca (2013) did not exhibit
279 inhibitory activity against *E. coli*, all our isolates did, in concordance with Giles-Gomez et al.
280 (2016).

281 The beer-spoilage ability was investigated as described in Suzuki (2002) and counts on MRS
282 agar plates were only obtained for 6 of the 29 isolates. Sakamoto & Konings (2003) reported that
283 microorganisms isolated from spoiled beer frequently fail to grow upon reinoculation in beer. The
284 evolution of counts for these 6 isolates are shown in Fig. 1. For all of these isolates, values of
285 counts decreased during the first eight days of incubation after which, for 5 out of them (F7-13; F3-
286 15; F6-3; BU-9 and F2-13), an increase at counts was observed, reaching values around higher than
287 10^4 cfu/mL, likely due to the acclimatization of these bacteria to beer or hop compounds.
288 Subsequently, evolution of counts varied with the isolates. So, while counts for isolates F7-13 and
289 F3-15 suffered a sharp decrease and growth was not observed on samples taken after 32 days of
290 incubation, counts for isolates F6-3, BU-9 and F2-13 went down very slowly reaching values
291 around 10^4 cfu/mL at the end of the 60 day incubation period.

292 Counts for isolate F12-19 decreased from the beginning until the end of incubation and
293 therefore growth did not occur during incubation. Growth was not observed in the non-inoculated
294 beer used as a control during incubation (data not shown).

295 In order to confirm that colonies grown on MRS agar plates belonged to the inoculated isolate,
296 a RAPD-PCR analysis with the primer M13 was carried out and the band profiles compared with
297 that of the inoculated isolate. Results confirmed that colonies grown on MRS agar plates for all six
298 isolates correspond to the inoculated isolate.

299 When the six isolates were examined for the presence of *horA* and *horC* hop resistance genes,
300 the results showed that none of them harboured any of these genes. *horA* gen, described by Sami et
301 al. (1997) in a hop-resistant *Lactobacillus brevis*, has also been found by Haakensen & Ziola (2008)
302 in isolates of *Pediococcus*, *Bacillus*, *Paenibacillus* and *Staphylococcus* and the authors affirm that
303 this finding suggests that *horA* gen exists in bacteria in environments beyond the breweries.
304 However, no reports describing the presence of *horA* and *horC* genes in *Leuconostoc* isolates have
305 been found. The presence of genes other than the analysed in this study or the existence of other
306 hop resistance mechanisms could explain the growth observed for 5 of the isolates in the beer
307 spoilage ability assay. Sakamoto & Konings (2003) reported that hop resistance in LAB does not
308 appear to be a general feature of all beer-spoiling bacteria and that a simple mechanism of hop
309 resistance does not exist, but rather they describe five different mechanisms.

310 Analysis of D-lactic acid and diacetyl in beers from the spoilage ability assay in which counts
311 had been obtained displayed very low concentrations for both compounds. Values for D-lactic acid
312 were lower than 0.16 g/L and diacetyl was not produced by any of the isolates.

313

314 **4. Conclusions**

315 Previously reported results have displayed that *Ln. mesenteroides* isolates isolated from beer
316 assessed in this study, were scarcely acidifying and proteolytic and therefore, their presence in beer

317 would not produce an excess of acidity or bitterness by the amino acids released. In addition, they
318 were negative for EPS production, thus avoiding turbidity that so negatively affects the quality of
319 the beer.

320 The enzymatic capacities of some of the isolates make them potentially interesting from a
321 technological point of view. As an example, the presence of glucosidases in B1-18 isolate could
322 contribute positively to the aroma and taste of beer as well as providing a health benefit by being a
323 probiotic isolate.

324 The antagonistic activity of the isolates against potentially pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli*
325 and *St. aureus* makes them very interesting, as they lower the risks for consumers as well as
326 decreasing the economic losses that the brewing industry may suffer as a result of these harmful
327 bacteria being present in the beer. Analyses of antagonistic activity against other indicator
328 organisms such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* or *Salmonella* would be advisable.

329 Finally, the beer-spoilage ability assay showed that only 5 out of 29 isolates were able to grow
330 in beer but none of them harboured *horA* or *horC* genes. However, the growth of these isolates in
331 beer produce neither an excess of D-lactic acid or diacetyl nor turbidity.

332 In summary, these findings show that the presence of the analysed *Ln. mesenteroides* isolates,
333 either during the brewing process or in the beer itself, would not negatively impact the beer but on
334 the contrary, the presence of some of them could produce interesting benefits.

335

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340

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Fig. 1. Counts for *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates obtained in the beer spoilage assay.

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Table 1

Primers used for PCR detection of hop resistance genes.

Target gene	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Reference
<i>horA</i>	ATCCGGCGGTGGCAAATCA AATCGCCAATCGTTGGCG	Suzuki et al. (2005)
<i>horC</i>	GTCAACGAAGACAAAGGAGCTCTC GGCGAACCGTGAACAAATAG	Suzuki et al. (2005)

Table 2Mean values \pm standard deviation of the enzymatic activities assayed in the *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates.

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Isolate	Acidifying activity*		Proteolytic activity**	Autolytic activity***		
	4 h	24 h		30 min	4 h	24 h
F7-18	0.12 \pm 0.01 ^{e,f}	0.57 \pm 0.03 ^c	0.33 \pm 0.01 ^a	2.77 \pm 0.09 ^{a,b}	8.42 \pm 0.13 ^{b,c,d}	21.15 \pm 1.47 ^a
F6-9	0.13 \pm 0.01 ^f	0.42 \pm 0.08 ^{b,c}	0.27 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.91 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	5.79 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b,c}	26.64 \pm 1.30 ^{a,b}
F7-14	0.13 \pm 0.02 ^f	0.58 \pm 0.03 ^c	0.21 \pm 0.06 ^a	2.75 \pm 0.10 ^{a,b}	8.46 \pm 0.22 ^{b,c,d}	20.55 \pm 1.11 ^a
F10-11	0.13 \pm 0.01 ^f	0.58 \pm 0.02 ^c	0.30 \pm 0.04 ^a	0.44 \pm 0.06 ^a	4.45 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	20.82 \pm 1.39 ^a
F7-13	0.12 \pm 0.00 ^{e,f}	0.56 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c}	0.26 \pm 0.03 ^a	2.83 \pm 0.09 ^{a,b}	10.57 \pm 0.83 ^{d,e}	27.68 \pm 1.52 ^{a,b,c}
F6-12	0.11 \pm 0.00 ^{d,e,f}	0.60 \pm 0.02 ^c	0.28 \pm 0.01 ^a	2.98 \pm 0.08 ^{a,b}	9.55 \pm 0.95 ^{c,d,e}	21.07 \pm 1.76 ^a
F2-11	0.08 \pm 0.03 ^{c,d,e}	0.49 \pm 0.07 ^{b,c}	0.46 \pm 0.02 ^b	2.14 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	8.78 \pm 0.46 ^{b,c,d}	26.24 \pm 0.90 ^{a,b}
F2-5	0.12 \pm 0.01 ^{e,f}	0.58 \pm 0.00 ^c	0.54 \pm 0.05 ^{b,c,d}	2.15 \pm 0.01 ^{a,b}	8.19 \pm 0.21 ^{b,c,d}	20.84 \pm 0.71 ^a
F2-3	0.06 \pm 0.05 ^{b,c}	0.50 \pm 0.08 ^{b,c}	0.51 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	2.95 \pm 0.03 ^{a,b}	8.79 \pm 0.88 ^{b,c,d}	22.32 \pm 1.55 ^{a,b}
F10-3	0.01 \pm 0.01 ^{a,b}	0.42 \pm 0.07 ^{b,c}	0.57 \pm 0.04 ^{b,c,d}	2.55 \pm 0.02 ^{a,b}	8.43 \pm 0.73 ^{b,c,d}	24.76 \pm 0.79 ^{a,b}
F2-13	0.01 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.40 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c}	0.50 \pm 0.02 ^{b,c}	5.21 \pm 0.05 ^{a,b,c}	4.04 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	45.53 \pm 0.85 ^{e,f}
F3-15	0.01 \pm 0.01 ^{a,b}	0.37 \pm 0.01 ^{b,c}	0.50 \pm 0.09 ^{b,c}	5.80 \pm 0.02 ^{b,c}	4.93 \pm 0.09 ^{a,b}	47.96 \pm 1.50 ^f
F4-15	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.36 \pm 0.02 ^{b,c}	0.62 \pm 0.02 ^{b,c,d}	3.38 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	2.80 \pm 0.05 ^a	40.51 \pm 1.79 ^{d,e,f}
F3-9	0.01 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.41 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c}	0.64 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	5.83 \pm 0.07 ^{b,c}	4.58 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}	47.12 \pm 0.61 ^f
F4-7	0.00 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.40 \pm 0.05 ^{b,c}	0.59 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	1.72 \pm 0.08 ^{a,b}	1.38 \pm 0.04 ^a	43.08 \pm 1.26 ^{e,f}
F6-3	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.41 \pm 0.04 ^{b,c}	0.57 \pm 0.05 ^{b,c,d}	9.27 \pm 0.02 ^c	8.16 \pm 0.27 ^{b,c,d}	45.21 \pm 1.63 ^{e,f}

F4-5	0.03 ± ± 0.02 ^{a,b}	0.37 ± ± 0.04 ^{b,c}	0.58 ± ± 0.04 ^{b,c,d}	5.72 ± ± 0.06 ^{b,c}	3.18 ± ± 0.02 ^a	36.70 ± ± 0.67 ^{c,d,e}
F4-3	0.02 ± ± 0.02 ^{a,b}	0.37 ± ± 0.04 ^{b,c}	0.55 ± ± 0.04 ^{b,c,d}	4.92 ± ± 0.02 ^{a,b}	5.79 ± ± 0.09 ^{a,b,c}	40.65 ± ± 1.18 ^{d,e,f}
F4-12	0.00 ± ± 0.00 ^a	0.31 ± ± 0.08 ^b	0.56 ± ± 0.05 ^{b,c,d}	3.13 ± ± 0.09 ^{a,b}	4.23 ± ± 0.07 ^{a,b}	45.38 ± ± 1.83 ^{e,f}
F12-12	0.00 ± ± 0.00 ^a	0.36 ± ± 0.01 ^{b,c}	0.69 ± ± 0.06 ^d	6.52 ± ± 0.03 ^{b,c}	4.83 ± ± 0.04 ^{a,b}	40.16 ± ± 1.41 ^{d,e,f}
B1-18	0.00 ± ± 0.00 ^a	0.12 ± ± 0.02 ^a	0.64 ± ± 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	3.73 ± ± 0.04 ^{a,b}	11.10 ± ± 0.84 ^{d,e}	31.90 ± ± 1.62 ^{b,c,d}
BU-13	0.03 ± ± 0.01 ^{a,b}	0.40 ± ± 0.04 ^{b,c}	0.59 ± ± 0.02 ^{b,c,d}	4.12 ± ± 0.09 ^{a,b}	13.54 ± ± 0.82 ^e	27.89 ± ± 1.04 ^{a,b,c}
BU-9	0.00 ± ± 0.01 ^a	0.38 ± ± 0.05 ^{b,c}	0.57 ± ± 0.07 ^{b,c,d}	5.39 ± ± 0.05 ^{b,c}	12.84 ± ± 1.49 ^{d,e}	29.94 ± ± 1.87 ^{a,b,c}
B1-3	0.01 ± ± 0.01 ^{a,b}	0.35 ± ± 0.02 ^{b,c}	0.61 ± ± 0.05 ^{b,c,d}	5.25 ± ± 0.05 ^{a,b,c}	12.02 ± ± 1.01 ^{d,e}	32.16 ± ± 1.66 ^{b,c,d}
BU-8	0.02 ± ± 0.04 ^{a,b}	0.41 ± ± 0.01 ^{b,c}	0.52 ± ± 0.07 ^{b,c,d}	5.74 ± ± 0.02 ^{b,c}	13.74 ± ± 1.07 ^e	30.49 ± ± 1.47 ^{a,b,c}
F12-19	0.09 ± ± 0.02 ^{c,d,e,f}	0.45 ± ± 0.03 ^{b,c}	0.56 ± ± 0.02 ^{b,c,d}	3.81 ± ± 0.05 ^{a,b}	11.49 ± ± 0.71 ^{d,e}	25.71 ± ± 1.77 ^{a,b}
B1-12	0.09 ± ± 0.01 ^{c,d,e,f}	0.46 ± ± 0.02 ^{b,c}	0.61 ± ± 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	4.62 ± ± 0.07 ^{a,b}	12.00 ± ± 1.04 ^{d,e}	30.08 ± ± 1.01 ^{a,b,c}
B1-9	0.07 ± ± 0.03 ^{c,d}	0.44 ± ± 0.08 ^{b,c}	0.62 ± ± 0.03 ^{b,c,d}	3.24 ± ± 0.05 ^{a,b}	11.42 ± ± 0.56 ^{d,e}	29.67 ± ± 1.58 ^{a,b,c}
F8-13	0.11 ± ± 0.01 ^{d,e,f}	0.51 ± ± 0.01 ^{b,c}	0.67 ± ± 0.05 ^{c,d}	4.07 ± ± 0.03 ^{a,b}	11.76 ± ± 0.95 ^{d,e}	26.27 ± ± 1.38 ^{a,b}

^{a-f} Mean values without a common superscript are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to the Student–Newman–Keuls test for each property assayed.

*ΔpH after 4 h and 24 h incubation.

**Results expressed as mmol Gly/L.

***Optical density decrease.

Table 3Enzymatic activities of some *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* isolates assessed using the API-ZYM galleries.

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Enzymatic activities	Isolate							
	F7-18	F7-14	F4-3	F6-3	F12-12	F8-13	B1-9	B1-18
Alkaline phosphatase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Esterase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Esterase lipase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lipase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Leucine arylamidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+++
Valine arylamidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	++
Cystine arylamidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Trypsin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
α -chymotrypsin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Acid phosphatase	+	++	+	++	+++	+	++	+
Naphthol-AS-BI-phosphohydrolase	w	w	+	+	+	+	+	+
α -galactosidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	w
β -galactosidase	-	-	-	-	w	w	-	+++
β -glucuronidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
α -glucosidase	-	-	-	-	+	+	w	++
β -glucosidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+++
N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
α -mannosidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
α -fucosidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(+) Positive reaction. The intensity of the colour was rated as light (+), medium (++) or dark (+++).

(-) Negative reaction.

(w) weak reaction.

Highlights

Ln. mesenteroides isolates were low acidifiers and proteolytic and any produced EPS

Some of the isolates produced beneficial enzymes

All the isolates could inhibit the growth of both *E. coli* and *St. aureus*

Five of the 29 isolates were able to grow in beer but any harboured *horA* or *horC* genes

Ln. mesenteroides in the brewing process could provide interesting benefits

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